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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE JOY OF LEARNING DRAFTING”

Drafting may sound serious and difficult to some students; they may think about the discipline and skills that they need to be able to draft something which can be a problem for those who haven't truly immersed in it but it can be an enjoyable and fulfilling experience.

Drafting combines creativity and problem-solving, it develops discipline at the same time develops creativity of the learner. If the teacher also makes the activities more relevant to real-world situations, this can help the students determine its importance and apply it when they are building their houses or buildings. Drafting can also become enjoyable because of the tools and technology involved which give the learners confidence and the feel of being artistic. Also introducing the learners to innovative technology that can be used in drafting is significant, this way when they are in their workplace they will be familiarized with the technology and equipment being used. Learning to navigate in applications can also be helpful for the learners which helps them unlock skills they never knew they had which gives them a sense of accomplishment. Finally, is its ability to awaken creativity and imagination in learners, the development of unique but incredibly functioning inventions provides possibilities and find solutions to real-world problems through visual representation.

Moreover, learning drafting is enjoyable because it connects to reality. This sense of purpose makes every drawing session exciting and meaningful; this makes the learners wonder what will they be doing next. The thought that their imagination can be turned into reality makes Drafting into a journey of fun and discovery.

